

The inclined throw in medium at small distances

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We introduce:

a = angle of throw $0^\circ \leq a \leq 90^\circ$

v_0 = initial velocity

g = earth's acceleration = $9.81 \frac{m}{s^2}$

We treat the inclined throw in a medium (air, gas) with constant density. For throws it is valid see Budo [1] §16 p.85 equation (22):

$$\begin{aligned}m\dot{v}_x &= -F(v) \cdot \frac{v_x}{v} \\m\dot{v}_y &= -mg - F(v) \cdot \frac{v_y}{v}\end{aligned}$$

with:

v = absolute value of the velocity

$$v(t) = |(v_x(t), v_y(t))| := \sqrt{v_x(t)^2 + v_y(t)^2}$$

t = time

m = mass of the ball

$F(v)$ = drag force in medium

The point over v means differentiation to the time.

We occupy with the case $F(v) = kv$. k is a certain constant. This is true at small velocities and small bodies. The both differential equations simplify to:

$$\begin{aligned}m\dot{v}_x &= -kv_x \\m\dot{v}_y &= -mg - kv_y\end{aligned}$$

If we insert $\dot{x} = v_x$ and $\dot{y} = v_y$, we get see Heuser [2] chapter 5 S.78:

$$x(t) = \frac{mv_0 \cos a}{k} \cdot \left(1 - e^{-\frac{kt}{m}}\right) \quad (1)$$

$$y(t) = \frac{m}{k} \cdot \left(v_0 \sin a + \frac{mg}{k} \right) \cdot \left(1 - e^{-\frac{kt}{m}} \right) - \frac{mgt}{k} \quad (2)$$

are the solutions of both differential equations.

We make the proof. First we derive:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x} &= v_0 \cos a e^{-\frac{kt}{m}} \\ \dot{y} &= \left(v_0 \sin a + \frac{mg}{k} \right) \cdot e^{-\frac{kt}{m}} - \frac{mg}{k} \end{aligned}$$

We calculate the second derivation:

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{x} &= -\frac{kv_0 \cos a}{m} \cdot e^{-\frac{kt}{m}} \\ \ddot{y} &= -\frac{k}{m} \cdot \left(v_0 \sin a + \frac{mg}{k} \right) \cdot e^{-\frac{kt}{m}} \end{aligned}$$

We construct:

$$\begin{aligned} m\ddot{x} &= -kv_0 \cos a \cdot e^{-\frac{kt}{m}} \\ m\ddot{y} &= -k \cdot \left(v_0 \sin a + \frac{mg}{k} \right) \cdot e^{-\frac{kt}{m}} \end{aligned}$$

It follows:

$$\begin{aligned} -mg - k\dot{y} &= -mg - k \cdot \left(v_0 \sin a + \frac{mg}{k} \right) \cdot e^{-\frac{kt}{m}} + mg \\ &= -k \cdot \left(v_0 \sin a + \frac{mg}{k} \right) \cdot e^{-\frac{kt}{m}} \end{aligned}$$

and:

$$-k\dot{x} = -kv_0 \cos a \cdot e^{-\frac{kt}{m}}$$

The functions $x(t)$ and $y(t)$ satisfy the differential equations. Then we view the initial conditions:

$$x(0) = 0 \quad y(0) = 0 \quad \dot{x}(0) = v_0 \cos a \quad \dot{y}(0) = v_0 \sin a$$

Thus we have done the proof. The duration of ascent is:

$$T = \frac{m}{k} \cdot \ln \left(1 + \frac{kv_0 \sin a}{mg} \right)$$

and the height of ascent:

$$H = \frac{mv_0 \sin a}{k} - \left(\frac{m}{k} \right)^2 \cdot g \cdot \ln \left(1 + \frac{kv_0 \sin a}{mg} \right)$$

see Heuser [2] p.591. The time of throw must be calculate from $y(t)=0$. We get the range of throw from $x(t)$, if we insert the time of throw in t . Now we

treat an example with $v_0 = 10$ metres per second. The radius of the thrown ball shall be 10cm. The ball's mass is 0.01 kg. We look at the throws with different angles of throw. $k = 6\pi\eta r$ is calculate with Stokes's law and has got the value 0.000032421 μPasm . The viscosity of air is 17.2 μPas . Then we can view the following table. Distances are presented in metres and times in seconds. The angle of throw will be shown in degree:

angle of throw	time of ascent	height of ascent	time of throw	range of throw
10	0.176	0.152	0.354	3.484
20	0.343	0.584	0.697	6.543
30	0.498	1.235	1.019	8.809
40	0.636	2.024	1.310	10.011
45	0.698	2.439	1.440	10.162
50	0.754	2.853	1.560	10.005
60	0.848	3.624	1.764	8.794
70	0.917	4.248	1.914	6.525
80	0.960	4.653	2.006	3.471
90	0.974	4.794	2.036	0

The linear drag force is only valid at small distance and at small velocities for example basket-ball fields.

References

- [1] A. Budo "Theoretische Mechanik" 10.edition VEB Deutscher Verlag der Wissenschaften Berlin 1980
- [2] Harro Heuser "Gewöhnliche Differentialgleichungen" 2.edition B.G. Teubner Stuttgart 1991